

The following document preceded the online survey.

**University of Wisconsin - Madison
Research Participant Information and Consent Form**

Study Title: Study of Madison park visitors to conservation and community parks

Description of the research

- You are invited to participate in a research study identifying characteristics of Madison Park visitors, including why you visited the park, your knowledge and perception of park mammals, and your nature relatedness.
- You have been asked to participate because you visited one of the community or conservation parks we are studying.
- The purpose of the research is to identify connections between park visitors, their mammal knowledge and perceptions, and their nature relatedness. This information can then be implemented into educational programming.
- This study will include adults 18 years or older that visit the targeted community or conservation parks.
- This research will be conducted at six Madison parks: Door Creek Park, Elver Park, Edna Taylor Conservation Park, Owen Conservation Park, Olin Park, and Turville Point Conservation Park.

What will my participation involve?

- If you decide to participate in this research, you will be asked to sign a consent form and complete an online survey of your visit to the park.
- Your participation will require 1 session that will last approximately 5 to 10 minutes.

Are there any risks to me?

We do not anticipate any risks to you from participation in this study. However, an unexpected risk of a breach of confidentiality may occur by participating in this study.

Are there any benefits to me?

We do not expect any direct benefits to you from participation in this study.

How will my confidentiality be protected?

- This study is confidential. Neither your name nor any other identifiable information will be published.
- Only approved personnel will have access to the data with any identifying factors being removed from the survey results and all data will be password protected, securely stored, and not be used or distributed for future research studies.

Whom should I contact if I have questions?

You may ask any questions about the research at any time. If you have questions about the research, you should contact Sheryl Hayes Hursh at hayeshursh@wisc.edu.

If you are not satisfied with the response of the research team, have more questions, or want to talk with someone about your rights as a research participant, you should contact the Education and Social/Behavioral Science IRB Office at 608-265-4312.

If you decide not to participate or to withdraw from the study, you may do so without penalty.

Checking the box below indicates that you have read this consent form, had an opportunity to ask any questions about your participation in this research, are 18 years of age or older, and voluntarily consent to participate. You will receive a copy of this form for your record, should you request one.

